

THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF PEDAGOGICAL PERSONNEL OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES OF HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. *The paper discusses the essence and content of the professional competence of foreign language teachers, as well as the pedagogical conditions and mechanisms of its formation and development based on innovative approaches.*

Keywords: *professional competence, readiness for professional activity, development of professional competence, teaching staff of foreign languages.*

The strategic development of all sectors of the socio-economic sphere in Uzbekistan, the expansion of international ties, the expansion of the tourism industry leads to the need for specialists who speak foreign languages, as well as the requirements for their level of training. A high level of ownership of a foreign language in such a situation becomes educational value. In this process, the pedagogical personnel of foreign languages of higher educational institutions play a special role and the requirements for their level of professional competence are growing.

The professional competence of pedagogical personnel is a holistic system that contains requirements for abilities, readiness for professional activity and personality traits and ensures the pedagogical ability and activities that are necessary for the implementation of effective pedagogical activity [1].

Currently, the development of the professional competence of pedagogical personnel of foreign languages of higher educational institutions is of urgent importance. The main priority areas of research in the field of the formation and development of professional competence are the development of scientifically based proposals to ensure the effectiveness of educational processes in higher educational institutions based on the introduction of innovative management methods, increasing the adaptability and flexibility of its functioning, taking into account specific socio-economic conditions. Therefore, the improvement of the processes of development of professional competence is an urgent task of pedagogical research [2].

Meanwhile, the problem of relevance of determining the requirements for the pedagogical staff of foreign languages and solving a number of problems arises:

- compilation of uniform requirements for the content and quality of professional activity (assessment of activities);
- planning professional development of pedagogical personnel, development of job descriptions.

In conducted scientific research on the problem of the formation and development of professional competence, there are a number of characteristic disadvantages, as a rule, related to the lack of accounting of modern requirements and ongoing changes in practice [3]. Thus, the issues of professional competence of pedagogical personnel in the higher education system, justification of the professional development strategy, as well as their practical implementation

remain insufficiently developed. Today's practice is very actualizing the scientific solution to these issues as the most optimal real practical needs, prospects for the development of higher education as a whole.

To organize effective pedagogical activity, pedagogical personnel must have at a sufficient level special knowledge about the organization of practical activities in accordance with the laws of the theory of pedagogy, respectively, professional competence depends on the amount of knowledge and skills. Most researchers associate the insufficient effectiveness of the professional activities of pedagogical personnel of foreign languages of higher educational institutions with the low level of functioning of the system of relevant information support, the essence of which should consist in effective support for the educational process [4].

Based on the foregoing, we identified three groups of competencies characterizing the professional competence of a modern teacher:

1. Personal competence, including the level of personal self -development and reflecting the personal position of the pedagogical activity of the teacher;
2. Social competence, implemented in conditions of professional activity in conditions of interaction with society;
3. Special competence containing a set of knowledge and skills involving a solution to specific pedagogical problems.

In our opinion, the development of the professional competence of pedagogical personnel should be innovative and ensure the achievement of the goals of a professional and pedagogical education, if the next set of organizational and pedagogical conditions is fulfilled:

- wide implementation of innovative methods in professional activities;
- ensuring the conformity of the content of the educational activity of the department with the level of professional qualities of pedagogical personnel;
- ensuring the productive and contextual nature of all types of self -education of pedagogical personnel;
- the presence of a system of methodological support for the development of intellectual and creative abilities of pedagogical personnel of a foreign language.

The study showed that it is impossible to single out the only correct approach to the definition of the "professional competence of pedagogical personnel", since it is an integrative concept and should be considered from different angles.

We believe that the professional competence of pedagogical personnel is not only its ability to holistically and deeply analyze, identify, accurately formulate problems, but also effectively realize approaches to their solution. Professional competence requires a certain set of personal qualities such as creativity, innovative thinking, readiness and ability to find innovative ideas and use the possibilities of their optimal implementation, a systemic, prognostic approach to the selection and organization of innovations, and the ability to introspection.

In our opinion, the formation and development of the professional competence of the pedagogical personnel of the highest educational institution, not only through their self -education and acquisition of practical experience in the process of professional activity, but also through their professional retraining or advanced training for various additional professional educational programs. For the implementation of the above tasks, we consider it very appropriate to organize the targeted training of pedagogical personnel of foreign languages in courses of retraining and advanced training.

Meanwhile, the self-education and self-development of pedagogical personnel of foreign languages in the process of professional activity contribute to the development of innovative preparedness, the acquisition by the teacher of professional experience, improving the quality, the effectiveness of educational activity in the highest educational institution. The implementation of self-education and self-development is based on a complex of pedagogical conditions taking into account the specifics of activity, the performance of tasks, the choice of content, forms and methods for each level of development of the professional competence of pedagogical personnel. At the same time, the choice of individual creative trajectory of self-development, its methodological and software is very important; Joint work with colleagues, participation in conferences, exhibitions of pedagogical achievements.

An analysis of theoretical aspects of solving the problem of the development of professional competence made it possible to determine a single approach to the interpretation of the leading concepts of our research.

We consider professional competence as a sustainable ability of pedagogical personnel to effective implementation of professional activities and educational tasks. We consider the process of developing professional competence as a complex and contradictory process of improving all aspects of a professionally competent person. The development of the professional competence of pedagogical personnel of foreign languages of higher educational institutions is ensured by the implementation of a complex of didactic techniques, which was developed by us, taking into account the characteristics of theoretical and practical training; In accordance with the complex of organizational and pedagogical conditions for the development of professional competence.

Thus, on the basis of the foregoing, we can conclude that the professional competence of pedagogical personnel of foreign languages in the higher education system is primarily a system of professional knowledge, skills and attitudes that manifest:

- constant self-ensuring mobility and replenishing professional knowledge;
- the ability to identify and creatively solve professional problems at the level of technological or labor standards;
- in the flexibility of the methods used and methods of practical activity;
- in the criticality of thinking, reflection, continuous professional growth, etc.

REFERENCES

1. Жилина А.И. Эталонная модель профессиональной компетентности менеджера (руководителя). Книга 3. – СПб.: ИОВ РАО, 2002. – 228 с.
2. Лазарев В. С, Мартиросян Б. П. Педагогическая инноватика: объект, предмет и основные понятия // Педагогика. - 2004. - N 4.
3. Ибрагимов, Г.И. Качество среднего профессионального образования в современных условиях / Г.И. Ибрагимов // Педагогика. – 2006. – № 6. – С. 75-82.
4. Иванов, Д. Компетентности и компетентностный подход в образовании / Д. Иванов. – М.: Чистые пруды, 2007. – 32 с.